

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

Deliverable title	Updated data management plan
Deliverable number	D65 (Del. Rel. No. D1.14)
Status	Final
Planned delivery date	29/02/2024
Actual date of issue	19/12/2024
Nature of deliverable	ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot
Lead partner	DKRZ
Dissemination level	Public

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programmes under grant agreement No 101003470

About this document

This report is reviewing the data management implementation, listing the type and sources of data produced, handled and stored until month 30, provides information on respective repositories and access conditions. If content is updated in this reviewed version of the DMP, it is preceded by “**UPDATE March 2024**” and is formatted in *italic* font.

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WP1

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Contents

1	Executive summary	5
2	Conclusion & Results	5
3	Project objectives	6
4	Detailed report on the deliverable: Updated Data Management Plan (DMP) for nextGEMS	9
4.1	General project information	9
4.1.1	Research question of the project	9
4.1.2	Research fields	9
4.1.3	Keywords	9
4.1.4	nextGEMS coordination	10
4.1.5	nextGEMS duration	10
4.1.6	Funder	10
4.1.7	nextGEMS partners	10
4.2	Data Summary	10
4.2.1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of nextGEMS?	10
4.2.2	What types and formats of data will be generated/collected in nextGEMS?	11
4.2.3	Do guidelines/manuals exist for a consistent organisation/handling of the data	11
4.2.4	Is any existing data reused in nextGEMS?	12
4.2.5	What is the expected size of the generated data?	12
4.2.6	To whom might the generated data be useful ('data utility')?	13
4.3	Compliance with the FAIR data guiding principles	13
4.4	Resources	16
4.4.1	Required IT resources	16
4.4.2	Required resources for making data FAIR	18
4.5	Data security	19
4.5.1	What provisions are in place for data security?	19
4.5.2	Reproducibility of the data produced in nextGEMS	19
4.5.3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	19
4.6	Partner institutions	20
4.7	Work package specific data management	22
4.7.1	Work package WP1 Coordination	22
4.7.2	Work package WP2 Model Development	24
4.7.3	Work package WP3 Production	28
4.7.4	Work package WP4/5 Storms & Radiation	31
4.7.5	Work package WP6/7 Storms & Ocean	35
4.7.6	Work package WP8/9 Storms & Land	38
4.7.7	Work package WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication	41

4.7.8	Work package WP11 Ethics requirements	44
5	Dissemination and uptake	46
5.1	Uptake by the targeted audience	46
5.2	This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience	46
6	Deliverable timeliness	46
7	Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any	46
8	Sustainability	47
9	Full track of dissemination activities	47
10	Full track of publications and IP	47

1 Executive summary

This Deliverable details how all data in nextGEMS is handled and how the project addresses compliance with the FAIR data principles. Further, every work package has contributed information regarding the research data workflows applied to proceed towards the project goals. This also applies to the processing of personal data which is related to the ethics deliverable D11.1. All information contained in this DMP is considered as preliminary and the DMP will be updated as nextGEMS progresses.

2 Conclusion & Results

In this DMP, we have detailed the approach of nextGEMS to comply with the FAIR data principles from the perspective of a project creating very large amounts of numerical model simulation output which becomes obsolete with every new step in model development. Making all data available according to the FAIR principles is technically and organisationally not possible – nextGEMS thus focuses on selected project outcomes to be made available according to the FAIR principles. All necessary information needed to handle and process data created in nextGEMS is documented in <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de> and is not contained in this DMP. That website is maintained by nextGEMS project scientists.

Further, we have collected information pertaining to project data from every work package. This information consists of contact details, data produced and reused, data dependencies between work packages, approaches to project-internal and global data-sharing and dissemination, and data archiving approaches. Due to the early stage of the nextGEMS project, all information given in this DMP is considered as preliminary and will be updated as the project progresses, i.e. the DMP is appropriately treated as a “living document”.

UPDATE March 2024: *Over the course of the nextGEMS project, the handling of data has undergone a significant evolution. At the beginning of the project, the simulation output data was handled and accessed as was common practice over the last decade or two, i.e. data available on regular grids, made available as netcdf files and accessed via their path on the parallel file system at DKRZ. By M30 of the project, simulation output is provided in small chunks in zarr format on HEALPix grid and accessed via intake catalogs using python notebooks. The efficiency of data access and processing has increased by orders of magnitude and the methods have been thoroughly tested in the nextGEMS hackathons. The online resource <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de> has proven to be essential for the success of the projects' data handling and management. The data handling methods developed in nextGEMS provide blueprints for rethinking and redesigning the way large-volume Earth System Model output data are managed.*

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	no
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | no |

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP1	Relevance in this deliverable?
Day to day project management	yes
Scientific coordination including quality assurance (KPI) and risk assessment	no
Data management	yes

Objectives of WP1	Relevance in this deliverable?
Ensure efficient innovation management, managing exploitation of project results	no
Supporting communication and dissemination activities	yes
Clustering with EC, regional and international projects/programmes	no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable: Updated Data Management Plan (DMP) for nextGEMS

4.1 General project information

4.1.1 Research question of the project

nextGEMS aims to develop and apply two Storm-Resolving Earth-system Models (SR-ESMs) to the study of anthropogenic climate change. To resolve a ‘storm’, in any colloquial sense of the term, requires a grid mesh of a few km. SR-ESMs thus differ qualitatively from ‘high-resolution’ (atmosphere: 30 km) versions of traditional ESMs, in that their tenfold finer grids allows them to explicitly represent essential climate processes which even the highest resolution climate models either neglect, or parametrise. SR-ESMs are envisioned as a Flagship Activity of the World Climate Research Programme, and as the substrate for ‘Digital Twins’, one of two scientific pillars for Europe’s new initiative, ‘Destination Earth’ (Bauer et al., 2021)¹.

By developing and applying two SR-ESMs, nextGEMS will lay a new foundation for Earth-system modeling in Europe; one which will provide a new platform for advancing the frontiers of climate-change science, while also supporting Europe’s central initiative for operationalizing the Paris Agreement and realizing its envisioned ‘Green Transition’.

4.1.2 Research fields

Natural Sciences / Atmospheric Science and Oceanography

4.1.3 Keywords

storm-resolving earth system model (SR-ESM)

climate change

ICON

IFS

stakeholder involvement

science communication

¹Bauer, P., Stevens, B. & Hazeleger, W. A digital twin of Earth for the green transition. Nat. Clim. Chang. 11, 80–83 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-021-00986-y>

4.1.4 nextGEMS coordination

The Max-Planck-Institute for Meteorology, Bundesstrasse 53, D-20146 Hamburg, Germany, is the coordinating institution.

4.1.5 nextGEMS duration

Sept. 1, 2021 to Aug. 31, 2025

4.1.6 Funder

Project funder: nextGEMS is funded through the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No - 101003470

4.1.7 nextGEMS partners

Please see the Appendix for a complete list of nextGEMS partners.

4.2 Data Summary

4.2.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of nextGEMS?

Data production in nextGEMS primarily concerns the performance of model simulations with a multitude of models (ICON, IFS, IFS-NEMO, IFS-FESOM, FESOM, ICON-O) and model configurations (coupled, atmosphere-only, ocean-only, coarse resolution, high resolution, storm-resolving resolution). In the course of the project, the SR-ESMs will be subject to a sequence of development cycles, each of which culminates in a hackathon involving the entire nextGEMS community plus external collaborators. The hackathons work with the output data from the then current version of the SR-ESMs, i.e. each hackathon uses a newly generated data set. At the hackathons, the model output is used to evaluate the current model performance by using available evaluation datasets in order to inform the model development tasks of the forthcoming development cycle. Further, the hackathons build the bridge to the downstream applications community by conceiving methods to inform renewable energy or fishery applications.

In the nextGEMS production phase, the SR-ESMs will produce data which will be made publicly available for general reuse through using available domain-specific and certified repositories, e.g. the World Data Center for Climate hosted at DKRZ.

Apart from the data generated for the development of the SR-ESM, other models and model setups are used to inform e.g. the design of physical parameterisations.

Another important aspect of nextGEMS is the communication concept to advertise the project goals and achievements to the general public. These efforts are supported by the generation and publication of videos - another form of data created in nextGEMS.

Survey data collected during and after the hackathons will inform a social network analysis.

Documentation facilitating the modeling and simulation workflow as well as multiple version of the project-wide data management plan will also be produced and made available to ensure efficient advancement towards the envisaged project goals.

4.2.2 What types and formats of data will be generated/collected in nextGEMS?

Earth System Model source code.

unstandardized Earth System Model output as GRIB and/or NetCDF files (structured or unstructured depending on model).

standardized SR-ESM model output for publication and long-term reuse.

collection of observational data products from e.g. satellites or super-sites.

audiovisual data (videos).

aggregated survey data in proprietary data format, published as report/paper.

UPDATE March 2024: *Unstandardized Earth System Model output in zarr-format (chunked data and rechunked) on HEALPix grid (multiple zoom levels)*

4.2.3 Do guidelines/manuals exist for a consistent organisation/handling of the data

Yes: <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de>, a growing online book that documents the nextGEMS datasets, their access and usage in form of executable scripts (see details in WP2)

UPDATE March 2024: *The online resource <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de> (easy.gems in the following) has been maintained and expanded in an operational manner throughout the project lifetime and its content reflects the advancements in model readiness, simulation execution and data handling. Specifically, the availability of and access to nextGEMS simulations from development cycles 2 and 3, as well as production runs, is documented. easy.gems has proven very useful in the preparation, execution and documentation of the nextGEMS hackathons. Note that the way nextGEMS data are accessed and processed has evolved significantly over the course of the project: at the beginning of the project, the simulation output data was handled and accessed as was common practice over the last decade or two, i.e. regridded data available on regular grids, made available as netcdf or GRIB files and accessed via their path on the parallel file system at DKRZ. The data were available as global fields with no regionalization. Key variables had been temporally averaged to monthly means before hackathons to allow for quicker analysis by the scientists at the events. This approach worked well given the amount of data to be handled, but it became obvious, that such an approach will not scale with increasing*

data amounts and complexity. For example, accessing global fields when a scientist is just interested in regional aspects is very time consuming and the "time-to-plot" was considered too long by project scientists. Starting from after the second NextGEMS hackathon in Vienna, at least ICON model output is made available in the zarr format. The data are chunked into small files and data access is orchestrated by using intake catalogs. Therefore, data access now follows a semantic approach and the scientists do not have to know the exact location of the data on the file system anymore. Furthermore, the model data are provided on the hierarchical HEALPix grid, which allows for the provision of model data at different resolutions at the same time. Hence, the computation of spatial and temporal averages is now significantly more efficient (or not needed anymore by the scientists). Therefore, by M30 of the project, the efficiency of data access and processing has increased by orders of magnitude and the methods have been thoroughly tested in the nextGEMS hackathons. The required shift in data handling approaches by the project members was enabled by the easy.gems resource.

4.2.4 Is any existing data reused in nextGEMS?

SR-ESM output from the DYAMOND initiative (<https://www.esiwave.eu/services/diamond-initiative>).

CMIP5 and CMIP6 data available via the ESGF or locally at DKRZ.

in-situ measurements from supersites (Cabauw, Lindenberg).

data products generated from satellite-based observations, e.g. from geostationary satellites (LandSAF products).

reanalysis datasets like ERA5.

proprietary, restricted data of IBEDROLA (IBEDROLA is an industry partner in nextGEMS).

Measurements from field campaigns, such as EUREC4A.

4.2.5 What is the expected size of the generated data?

Currently, only the anticipated data volume until the end of 2022 can be clearly estimated, because the resource allocation requests at the utilized HPC centers cover only one year.

Estimate at the state of the DMP: > 2 PB of SR-ESM output and supporting data, e.g. ocean spinups.

Please see details regarding the anticipated data production in the Appendix, especially WP2 and WP3.

Model source code data volume is negligible.

UPDATE 28 June 2023: for 2023, the granted storage space on the DKRZ parallel file system is 1.6PB, with an exception of 2.8 PB until 30 June 2023. The project scientists are in the process of moving large volumes of SR-ESM output to the DKRZ tape archive.

UPDATE March 2024: *for 2024, the granted storage space on the DKRZ parallel file system is 2.4 PB, with an exception of 5.5 PB until 31 May 2024. Of these 5.5 PB, approximately 5.4 PB are utilised at the time of writing. Together with DKRZ staff, the project scientists are preparing data handling workflows to move large volumes of the produced data to either the DKRZ tape archive or other storage tiers.*

4.2.6 To whom might the generated data be useful ('data utility')?

The data, data products and tools produced within nextGEMS are of interest to a variety of stakeholder groups. These are

1. the global weather and climate science community
2. research communities investigating the impact of anthropogenic climate change, e.g. agriculture, fisheries or ecology
3. industry, e.g. the renewable energy sector

Furthermore, nextGEMS communication activities, e.g. the publication of videos, science explainers, storylines and policy briefs, allow for a broad dissemination of project outcomes to the general public.

UPDATE March 2024: *nextGEMS data products have been accessed and downloaded by NVIDIA in 2023.*

4.3 Compliance with the FAIR data guiding principles

Which nextGEMS data will be made available in-line with the FAIR data principles? The FAIR data principles are applicable for data intended for long-term reuse. In highly data intensive simulation-based projects in Earth System Science such as nextGEMS, it is impractical to ensure sustained access to all produced data. The main task of nextGEMS is the development of the ICON and IFS SR-ESMs. This involves a multitude of development cycles, each of which produces several hundred TeraBytes of model output, until a final model version is obtained. Therefore, "data" produced in nextGEMS is first and foremost software. The output produced by this software is of course relevant for downstream reuse, but not the main focus of the project. Thus, the output from model development activities will not all be saved for long-term use. However, the code version, boundary conditions and general workflow procedures will be preserved in the source code repositories maintained at the modeling centers (MPI-M, ECMWF, AWI). In nextGEMS, the data made available for reuse in-line with the FAIR principles will be the following:

- selected simulation datasets in the scope of project deliverables (D2.2, D3.1 and D3.2)
- data underlying scientific publications or public project deliverables, e.g. model source code (depending on code license), analysis scripts, selected model output, selected post-processed datasets, workflow documentation

- All data produced by IFS within nextGEMS are freely and openly available.

Project data will be preserved and made available through FAIR-enabling repositories, such as the World Data Center for Climate (WDCC, suitable for model output and software), DKRZ's long-term archival service DOKU or other similar (institutional) repositories located close to the partner institutions. The WDCC is hosted at the German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ) - which is also a project partner in nextGEMS. Appropriate arrangements ensuring the provision of long-term archiving services are therefore in place.

UPDATE 28 June 2023: in accordance with D2.2, selected simulation datasets from cycle 2 were published via the WDCC and can be cited and found using the following information:

Wieners, Karl-Hermann; Ziemer, Florian Andreas; Koldunov, Nikolay; Pedruzo-Bagazgoitia, Xabier; Rackow, Thomas; Redler, René; Sidorenko, Dmitry; Kölling, Tobias (2023). nextGEMS: output of the model development cycle 2 simulations for ICON and IFS. World Data Center for Climate (WDCC) at DKRZ. https://doi.org/10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_cyc2

UPDATE March 2024: in accordance with D3.1, selected simulation datasets from cycle 3 were published via the WDCC and can be cited and found using the following information:

Koldunov, Nikolay; Kölling, Tobias; Pedruzo-Bagazgoitia, Xabier; Rackow, Thomas; Redler, René; Sidorenko, Dmitry; Wieners, Karl-Hermann; Ziemer, Florian Andreas (2023). nextGEMS: output of the model development cycle 3 simulations for ICON and IFS. World Data Center for Climate (WDCC) at DKRZ. https://doi.org/10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_cyc3.

The preparation of the publication of the nextGEMS production runs (D3.2) is ongoing at the time of writing. The production runs encompass 30 years of SR-ESM output from the ICON and IFS-FESOM models and amount to a total data volume of about 1 PB. Due to the data volume and nature of the data layouts used in day-to-day analysis (chunked zarr data on HEALPix grid), alternative data publishing methods will be considered. This is because the employed data structures and access methods are not compatible with the hardware configuration of the WDCC tape archive. The goal of D3.2 is to make the nextGEMS production runs available to the community in a way that allows semantic-driven data access via published data catalogs. Documentation of data access and processing methodologies will be made available alongside in order to ensure alignment with the FAIR data principles as much as possible. Note that data FAIRness is a continuum.

Findability Publication of the simulation output in the scope of project deliverables will be performed via the WDCC (World Data Center for Climate, hosted at DKRZ). The WDCC is a CoreTrustSeal certified domain-specific repository focusing on the long-term preservation and curation of climate model output.

The archived nextGEMS data will have persistent identifiers (PIDs) in the form of Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) assigned. The DOI-assignment follows WDCC guidelines and, among others, requires supplying rich, domain specific metadata (<https://cera-www.dkrz.de/docs/CERA2MetadataSubmissionGuide.pdf>). WDCC-archived (meta)data follow domain-specific standards, e.g. CF (<https://cfconventions.org/>). WDCC-archived data is findable via the WDCC search interface (<https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cerasearch/q>) and is also indexed in

external data catalogs (e.g. Google dataset search, EUDAT B2FIND, DWD WIS-Portal). Keywords are provided and searchable. Version numbers are not provided, because every new data publication at WDCC receives a new DOI (relations to previous “versions” are documented). DKRZ staff will assist the project scientists in compiling the essential metadata and preparing of the data to maximise long-term reusability. Publication-related data archived in DOKU are also assigned a persistent identifier and are findable via the above mentioned search interface.

Further, a list of all published and available nextGEMS data products will be maintained at the projects’ Zenodo page: <https://zenodo.org/communities/nextGEMS-h2020>

Accessibility As mentioned above, the selected simulation output will be published via the WDCC (deliverables D2.2, D3.1 and D3.2). Data access follows WDCC-implementations, which are the use of authentication procedures (everybody is free to register for an account) and standard and open data transfer protocols. No special software is needed to access the data. Data access is free of charge.

Model source code developments will be made accessible as follows:

- ICON and ICON-ocean model source code is available from the MPI-M git repository after agreeing to a usage license (https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/iconpublic/wiki/How_to_obtain_the_model_code) and following the instructions detailed on that web page. Publication of ICON code is not possible under the current licence.
- Model codes developed at ECMWF are the intellectual property of ECMWF and its member states, and therefore the IFS code is not publicly available. Access to a reduced version of the IFS code may be obtained from ECMWF under an OpenIFS licence (see <http://www.ecmwf.int/en/research/projects/openifs> for further information, last access: 23 March 2022). The nextGEMS IFS baseline cycle 47r3 will be available under OpenIFS in the near future.
- The FESOM ocean model is open source and available via GitHub: <https://github.com/FESOM/fesom2>. All necessary information regarding reuse and referencing of the model are documented on the FESOM projects GitHub page.

UPDATE March 2024: *Accessibility of the nextGEMS production runs associated with D3.2 will differ from that of D2.2 and D3.1. Please see Section 4.7.3 for details.*

- *ICON model code is available as Open Source since January 2024. More information and access to the code is available at <https://icon-model.org>.*
- *The currently available OpenIFS release is 48r1, which includes a plethora of model improvements stemming from nextGEMS investigations.*

Interoperability The selected model output made available via the WDCC will be prepared in accordance with domain-specific (meta)data standards, such as the CF or CMIP naming conventions. This is a prerequisite of data preservation in WDCC. The file format will be netCDF or GRIB/GRIB2, which are both open, and in the case of netCDF self-describing, file formats being the de-facto standard in simulation-based climate science. NetCDF and GRIB/GRIB2

data are accessible and processable by any software making use of the netCDF and/or GRIB libraries, e.g. python, R, Julia, NCL or CDOs. If (meta)data naming does, for any reason, not comply with any of the above standards, mapping tables are provided at <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/>. In WDCC, the data will be available as structured global arrays with standardised coordinate variables. This allows for combination with any dataset available on a structured and geo-referenced grid.

UPDATE March 2024: *The data published according to D2.2 and D3.1 follows the above interoperability approach. The datasets published according to D3.2 will be primarily made available in the zarr file format and accessed via catalogs (intake and/or STAC). Accessing the data requires specialized functionalities available in Python. Example analysis routines and tutorials will be provided in D3.2.*

Reusability The model simulation output published via the WDCC in the scope of project deliverables D2.2, D3.1 and D3.2 will be made available under the CC-BY 4.0 license. Further, these data are supplied with rich domain-specific metadata facilitating reuse.

Model source code developments are reusable following the licensing frameworks of the individual institutions:

- MPI-M: https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/iconpublic/wiki/How_to_obtain_the_model_code
- AWI: FESOM open source code available via GitHub (<https://github.com/FESOM/fesom2>)
References are given on the GitHub page
- ECMWF: Research access to IFS code is facilitated through the freely available OpenIFS licence and ECMWF makes available an increasing number of code modules under an open-source compatible licence. The nextGEMS baseline cycle 47r3 will be available under OpenIFS in the near future.

UPDATE March 2024: *As mentioned above, ICON model code has been made available as Open Source in January 2024. Further information is found at <https://icon-model.org>. Regarding IFS, the current OpenIFS release is based on 48r1, which contains several updates stemming from nextGEMS efforts. The IFS production runs in nextGEMS contain developments which will be made available in the next OpenIFS release (49r1) or later.*

4.4 Resources

4.4.1 Required IT resources

The following IT-resources needed for the successful conductance of nextGEMS are as follows:

- required IT resources at DKRZ have been applied for.
- required IT resources at an HPC facility other than DKRZ have been applied for.

Status of the application for IT-resources:

DKRZ resources: the following resources at DKRZ for 2022 were requested in the application round at the end of 2021:

- compute: 1 572 000 node hours
- disk storage: 1025 TB
- /arch/ storage: 1625 TB
- long-term archive (DOKU): 0

Of this request, the following amounts were granted:

- compute: 943 200 node hours
- disk storage: 718 TB
- /arch/ storage: 1625 TB
- long-term archive (DOKU): 0

Additional to the resources requested at DKRZ, nextGEMS also applied for compute resources at Jülich Supercomputing Center for performing nextGEMS simulations on JEWELS-BOOSTER. The request was granted. See details of WP2 for more details or check the [online reference to approved PRACE grants](#). Resources for the upcoming years of nextGEMS will be applied for in the framework of the common HPC resource application cycles.

UPDATE 28 June 2023: For 2023, the following HPC resources were granted at DKRZ:

- compute: 730 440 node hours
- disk storage: 1643 TB
- /arch/ storage: 540 TB
- long-term archive (DOKU): 192 TB

The project was granted an exceptional quota of 2800 TB of disk space until 30 June 2023. This amount of disk space was needed to accommodate the resource requirements during the Cycle 3 Hackathon in Madrid, which was held from 29 May - 2 June 2023 in Madrid.

The resource allocation at JSC for computations on JUWELS mentioned above was only partly used for a short simulation with the IFS model. All ICON model simulation used in Cycle 2 and 3 were performed at DKRZ.

All Cycle2 simulations with the IFS model were performed at the ECMWF facility in Bologna and the output data was then copied to DKRZ. For Cycle3, the 4.4km IFS run was performed at DKRZ, all other runs were again performed in Bologna and the output data was copied to DKRZ.

UPDATE March 2024: For 2024, the following HPC resources were granted (and utilised at time of writing) at DKRZ:

- *compute:*
 - CPU: 860570 node hours (667561 utilised)
 - GPU: 34000 node hours (0 utilised)
- *disk storage:* 2448 TiB, with exception of 5500 TiB until 31 March 2024 (5366 utilised)
- */arch/ storage:* 1566 TiB (0 utilised)
- *Swift Object Storage:* 10240 GiB (7189 utilised)

The main IFS Cycle 3 simulation was run at DKRZ. The remaining Cycle 3 IFS runs were performed at the ECMWF facility in Bologna and then copied to DKRZ. The 30 year IFS production run was performed at DKRZ. All Cycle 2, Cycle3 and production runs with ICON were performed at DKRZ.

UPDATE December 2024: In order to cope with the problem of increasing storage use on DKRZ's Levante cluster by the NextGEMS consortium, DKRZ management has decided to establish an interim data project to relieve the NextGEMS project storage quota. Currently, this interim project has an assigned storage quota of 1.5PB with 0.9PB being utilised. This interim storage project is administered by DKRZ's Data Management department.

This step was necessary because the model simulation output could not be transferred to DKRZ's tape archive in an efficient manner due to problems with DKRZ storage hardware. When the NextGEMS model output is moved to this interim data project, the requirement is that data ownership is transferred to DKRZ Data Management and that the data must not be altered anymore. By enforcing these requirements, it can be assured that links in catalogs, e.g. intake or STAC, which are used to access the data do not break. Once the DKRZ tape archive can be used as part of an operational data handling workflow, the data will be transferred to tape and removed from disk. Current work is in progress to investigate methods of making zarr-datasets efficiently handleable by a tape archive.

4.4.2 Required resources for making data FAIR

No additional resources apart from those supplied by the funder (6PM funding) are required for making the nextGEMS data FAIR. Long-term preservation of data in e.g. the WDCC is free of charge. Domain-specific advice on data preparation is a general DKRZ service available to the entire German climate science community, hence also nextGEMS.

UPDATE March 2024: The data handling methods and workflows are under constant development in nextGEMS. These developments represent a shared effort of project partners, with those from ECMWF, AWI, MPIM and DKRZ contributing most. The efforts are reflected in the growing *easy.gems* resource. This DMP merely represents a top-level summary of these efforts.

4.5 Data security

4.5.1 What provisions are in place for data security?

The model source code developments are performed using automatically backed-up repositories such as GitHub. The GitHub instance used to develop the ICON model is hosted at DKRZ. The FESOM git-repository is hosted on the general GitHub instance. Model output is stored on hard-disk or on tape. In case of hardware failure, the data can be recomputed.

It is in the responsibility of individual nextGEMS scientists to ensure the safety of their personal analysis routines and results by employing good data management practice in their day-to-day workflow, such as ensuring that essential methodological and analytical information is stored in automatically backed-up sections of the used infrastructure. E.g., the \$HOME directories of every user at DKRZ supply ample storage space and are backed-up daily.

Access to the HPC systems where the model output data are stored is restricted to accredited users of the respective HPC infrastructure. If desired, access to the nextGEMS data can be restricted to project members. This is however not anticipated, as the expected interest in the generated data spans a multitude of different user groups.

4.5.2 Reproducibility of the data produced in nextGEMS

Climate model simulation output can be reproduced given the workflows used to create particular output sets are preserved.

Model source code is maintained in institutional and backed-up code repositories. Unless these repositories don't fail, model source code is reproducible.

Post-processed data products can be reproduced given that workflow reproducibility is ensured.

Observational products used for analysis can be obtained from third-party data holdings, as nextGEMS itself does not produce observational data products.

4.5.3 Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?

nextGEMS data selected for long-term archival, preservation and curation will be stored in domain-specific and certified repositories such as WDCC or PANGAEA. Project data underlying scientific publications and or which is required as a documentation of project progress will be long-term archived using high-quality institutional services such as DKRZ's DOKU or KITs RADAR4KIT services.

4.6 Partner institutions

MPI-M

Full name and contact details: MAX-PLANCK-GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FÖRDERUNG DER WISSENSCHAFTEN EV, MAX-PLANCK INSTITUT FÜR METEOROLOGIE (Hamburg, Germany)

ECMWF

Full name and contact details: EUROPEAN CENTRE FOR MEDIUM-RANGE WEATHER FORECASTS

AWI

Full name and contact details: ALFRED-WEGENER-INSTITUT HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FÜR POLAR UND MEERESFORSCHUNG

UiB

Full name and contact details: UNIVERSITETET I BERGEN

UCPH

Full name and contact details: KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET

CNRS

Full name and contact details: CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE

MISU

Full name and contact details: STOCKHOLMS UNIVERSITET

UW

Full name and contact details: UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI

UOXF

Full name and contact details: THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD

GEOMAR

Full name and contact details: HELMHOLTZ ZENTRUM FÜR OZEANFORSCHUNG KIEL

BSC

Full name and contact details: BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER - CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION

UREAD

Full name and contact details: THE UNIVERSITY OF READING

WU

Full name and contact details: WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY

ETHZ

Full name and contact details: EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH

UBERN

Full name and contact details: UNIVERSITAET BERN

IPMA

Full name and contact details: INSTITUTO PORTUGUES DO MAR E DA ATMOSFERA IP

UH

Full name and contact details: HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO

UNITN

Full name and contact details: UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TRENTO

DKRZ

Full name and contact details: DEUTSCHES KLIMARECHENZENTRUM GMBH

UCM

Full name and contact details: UNIVERSIDAD COMPLUTENSE DE MADRID

IRD

Full name and contact details: INSTITUT DE RECHERCHE POUR LE DEVELOPPEMENT

IBE

Full name and contact details: IBERDROLA RENOVABLES ENERGIA SA

ISRA

Full name and contact details: INSTITUT SENEGALAIS DE RECHERCHES AGRICOLES

LT

Full name and contact details: LATEST THINKING GMBH

KIT

Full name and contact details: KARLSRUHER INSTITUT FUER TECHNOLOGIE

UHH

Full name and contact details: UNIVERSITAET HAMBURG

4.7 Work package specific data management

4.7.1 Work package WP1 Coordination

Overarching goals of WP1 Coordination

The overall objective of the Management Work Package is to ensure an effective implementation of the project, to deliver high-quality work standards and innovation actions, and to implement successful collaboration in different settings. The major activities comprise

- Day to day project management.
- Scientific coordination including quality assurance (KPI) and risk assessment (Critical Risks).
- Data management.
- Ensure efficient innovation management, managing exploitation of project results.
- Supporting communication and dissemination activities.
- Clustering with EC, regional and international projects/programmes.

Data categories produced in WP1 Coordination

other: Data Management Plan, web page, project organisation data

Specific datasets produced in WP1 Coordination

Data Management Plan.

Web page(s): <https://nextGEMS-h2020.eu/>.

project internal and personal data of project scientists.

UPDATE March 2024: *Project deliverables intended for public dissemination are all available at <https://nextGEMS-h2020.eu/partner-area/>. No login is required, the documents are found in the bottom-most section entitled “Deliverables and other reports”.*

Parameters/variables which the datasets produced in WP1 Coordination focus on

not applicable to this WP

Is input from other nextGEMS work packages relevant for work in WP1 Coordination?

Yes

Every WP

As early as possible

Does work in WP1 Coordination depend on external data sources?

No

Actual or expected size of the data produced in WP1 Coordination?

less than 1TB.

Measures taken in WP1 Coordination to reduce storage load on shared disk space during the runtime of nextGEMS:

not applicable to this WP.

Will regular backups of data produced in WP1 Coordination be performed?

yes, of selected data: DMP content is daily backed-up (<https://rdmo.dkrz.de>), web content backups as performed by the provider); project/personal data stored/backed-up by GWDG cloud service (owncloud) and external hard disk.

If yes, who is responsible for performing the backups in WP1 Coordination?

RDMO: DKRZ data management (cron job runs daily).

Web content: provider of web resources.

Project/personal data: GWDG and nextGEMS project office.

nextGEMS -internal use of data produced in WP1 Coordination:

nextGEMS DMP: project-internal communication of data-related aspects.

nextGEMS Webpages: communication and dissemination, orientation for project scientists.

project/personal data: project coordination.

Organization of nextGEMS -internal collaboration based on data produced in WP1 Coordination:

The nextGEMS DMP is made available via the nextGEMS cloud store. Further, public releases will be openly released according to EU guidelines for Open Research Data Pilots.

Will data produced in WP1 Coordination be published or shared?

Yes, internally for project partners: administrative project data.

Yes, externally for everyone: DMP (public deliverable), website.

No: personal data.

If yes, by which means will data produced in WP1 Coordination be published or shared?

Data Management Plan (DMP): the nextGEMS DMP will be made available via the channels made foreseen by the EU.

Website: openly accessible.

When will the data produced in WP1 Coordination be published or shared?

in accordance with project planning of deliverables.

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) produced in WP1 Coordination be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Has not yet been decided.

4.7.2 Work package WP2 Model Development

Overarching goals of WP2 Model Development

- To perform the Cycle 2 and initiate the Cycle 3 simulations of the Development Phase.
- To address errors and fine-tune the SR-ESMs, including associated output and data management strategies, based on feedback from, and together with, the S&R, S&O, S&L themes.
- To implement selected applications in SR-ESMs in collaboration with the four themes and users.
- To organise scrums to address data management and data analysis workflows in support of Hackathons and simulations analysis within nextGEMS and beyond.

Data categories produced in WP2 Model Development

climate model output: ECMWF: IFS-FESOM2, MPI-M: ICON-ESM.

software/tool: ICON, IFS, FESOM, NEMO.

other: project-wide data documentation wiki/homepage: <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de>.

Specific datasets produced in WP2 Model Development

ECMWF: IFS-FESOM for nextGEMS Cycle 2 (IFS TCo2559 (4.5 km) coupled to FESOM2 (8 km) for 6-12 months), IFS TCo3999 (2.8 km) coupled to FESOM2 (4 km) for two selected seasons (e.g. winter and summer).

MPI-M: ICON-ESM for nextGEMS Cycle 2: ICON (5 km, coupled) for 1-2 years, ICON (5 km, coupled) for 3 months.

ECMWF @JSC: IFS-FESOM, 2.8km atmosphere, 4 km ocean, 6 months AND 2 or 4 years in length.

ECMWF: simulations mirroring the above (IFS@8km with FESOM2).

MPI-M: simulations mirroring the above (ICON @10km).

MPI-M@JSC: ICON-ICON ocean, 2.5km atmosphere, 2.5 or 5km ocean, 6 months AND 2 or 4 years in length.

DKRZ: DKRZ will establish and maintain, with the input from project scientists, the simulation and analysis wiki maintained at <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de> (see also Deliverable D2.1). This resource will form the central information portal regarding usability and accessibility of nextGEMS simulation output at the project-level. This information is essential for the successful conductance of nextGEMS Hackathons and the general information of the overall consortium.

UPDATE 28 June 2023: an overview of simulations performed with ICON and IFS in preparation for the Cycle2 and Cycle3 hackathons is provided at <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de>

Parameters/variables which the datasets produced in WP2 Model Development focus on

ECMWF, MPI-M: IFS-FESOM2 and ICON output for Cycle 2 simulations will be informed by the experiences from the first nextGEMS hackathon. Output is documented at <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/>

ECMWF, MPI-M: IFS-FESOM2 and ICON output for Cycle 3 simulations is tbd.

UPDATE 28 June 2023: an overview of simulations performed with ICON and IFS in preparation for the Cycle2 and Cycle3 hackathons, as well as the variables provided, is provided at <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de>.

Is input from other nextGEMS work packages relevant for work in WP2 Model Development?

Yes

WP6: ocean spinup

as soon as possible

Does work in WP2 Model Development depend on external data sources?

No

Actual or expected size of the data produced in WP2 Model Development?

more than 1PB: JSC: >600TB (IFS and ICON), DKRZ: ICON 1,025 PB, ECMWF: IFS up to 500 TB.

UPDATE 28 June 2023: resources at JSC were NOT completely utilised (only one short IFS simulation was performed there). Data volumes exceed 3 PB in total. Data volume statistics and available datasets are documented at <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de>

Measures taken in WP2 Model Development to reduce storage load on shared disk space during the runtime of nextGEMS:

reduction of model output volume, e.g. compression, reduction of output frequency and/or variables (please specify shortly): set of output variables adapted to the findings of the first hackathon.

automated transfer to tape archive during model runtime, incl. appropriate documentation and/or metadata capture.

deletion of superfluous data.

transfer of not frequently used datasets to tape archive.

other: transfer of data from JSC to DKRZ.

UPDATE 28 June 2023: resources at JSC were not utilised. Further, nextGEMS project developments have resulted in novel data and output handling (e.g. compressed zarr data, usage of HEALPix grid). See <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de> for more information. Data transfer to tape was/is done after each Hackathon.

Will regular backups of data produced in WP2 Model Development be performed?

yes, of model/tool source code.

If yes, who is responsible for performing the backups in WP2 Model Development?

ECMWF model development team

ICON model development team

FESOM model development team

nextGEMS -internal use of data produced in WP2 Model Development:

SR-ESM output produced in WP2 forms the basis for successful nextGEMS hackathons. nextGEMS hackathons focus on fine-tuning and preparing the models for production runs.

nextGEMS analysis wiki (<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de>) will provide the central reference document for all project-internal simulation data access, processing and evaluation methods.

Model source code developments will be used to perform simulations and result in SR-ESMs ready for nextGEMS production runs to inform the projects' Application phase.

UPDATE March 2024: *The simulations resulting from the model development efforts during Cycle 2 and Cycle 3 have formed the basis for the successful Cycle 2 and Cycle 3 hackathons in Vienna and Madrid, respectively. Documentation of the produced data and how to access it is available via easy.gems.*

Organization of nextGEMS -internal collaboration based on data produced in WP2 Model Development:

The current state, availability, format and content of SR-ESM output is documented at <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de>. This web instance is maintained by DKRZ and critically relies on timely and accurate input of project scientists in order to serve the intended purpose.

The data of nextGEMS Cycle2 and Cycle3 simulations is/will be made available at DKRZ.

Each model development cycle of nextGEMS culminates in a Hackathon at which the output of the corresponding simulations (Cycle 2 and Cycle 3 simulations) is analysed. The findings inform the next development cycle.

ECMWF: Cycle 2 simulations with IFS-FESOM2 will be performed at Juwels. Data needs to be copied to DKRZ, similar to the strategy for ICON that we will adopt. Simulations are to be started early this year. Format is expected to be similar if not identical to Cycle 1 IFS output. The data is made available to everyone at the DKRZ supercomputer, as was done for the Cycle 1 simulations analyzed during the first Hackathon.

MPI-M: Cycle 2 and Cycle 3 simulations are performed at DKRZ and at JSC. The data produced at JSC will have to be transferred to DKRZ to make it available for analysis. This is also necessary because storage quotas at JSC are comparatively small (ca 100TB in total).

DKRZ: provision of an accurate and up-to-date nextGEMS analysis wiki critically depends on timely and precise input from the modeller providing the output data.

UPDATE March 2024: *The internal collaboration based on datasets produced in WP2 has been successful as described above. The availability of and methods to access the nextGEMS data are described in easy.gems.*

Will data produced in WP2 Model Development be published or shared?

Yes, internally for project partners: Cycle 2 and Cycle 3 model output needed for the hackathons; model source code.

Yes, externally for everyone: simulation output published via deliverables D2.2.

UPDATE 28 June 2023: the nextGEMS data published in connection with D2.2 (DOI: https://doi.org/10.26050/WDC/nextGEMS_cyc2)

If yes, by which means will data produced in WP2 Model Development be published or shared?

D2.2 Release (publishing in the sense of DOI provision) of selected Cycle 2 Simulations. (Task 2.2) (M14, MPI-M) (publication in WDCC with DOI), exact amount and content of published data is tbd.

UPDATE 28 June 2023: see above

D2.1 analysis wiki is accessible for interested outside users, as it is an openly accessible web page (<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de>).

Model source code is available via institutional repositories following the respective licensing agreements (see Sec. 3).

When will the data produced in WP2 Model Development be published or shared?

Publication of data (standardised simulation output) will happen according to the timeline defined by the deliverables laid out in the project grand agreement; primary data underlying scientific publications will be published according to FAIR data principles at the time required by the publisher.

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) produced in WP2 Model Development be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Discipline specific data center: WDCC

Other: DKRZ web-server (analysis wiki), GitHub (model source code)

4.7.3 Work package WP3 Production

Overarching goals of WP3 Production

- To complete Cycle 3 (Development) simulations.
- To finalize the configuration (including associated output and data management requirements) of SR-ESMs for the production simulations.
- To perform present day and future projections (i.e., production simulations).
- To organize and curate simulation output for sustainable access beyond the completion of nextGEMS.
- To support the four themes in exploring extensions of SR-ESMs to address additional application needs and testing proposed model improvements.

Data categories produced in WP3 Production

climate model output: IFS and ICON SR-ESMs in final configuration.

Specific datasets produced in WP3 Production

Two (ICON and IFS) climate projections for the period between 2020-2049 with a target horizontal resolution of 2 km to 3 km.

UPDATE March 2024: *In order to achieve sufficient simulation throughput and to be in line with the model developments after the Cycle 3 hackathon, the spatial resolution achieved for the 30 year nextGEMS production runs with ICON is 10km in the atmosphere and 5km in the ocean. For IFS-FESOM, the achieved resolutions are 9km and 5km for atmosphere and ocean, respectively. Documentation of these data is available via easy.gems or via the “4th km scale hackathon” event homepage: <https://mpim-po.pages.gwdg.de/km-scale-hackathon/>.*

Parameters/variables which the datasets produced in WP3 Production focus on

The exact content and scope of production runs is tbd.

UPDATE March 2024: *The documentation of the production runs is available on easy.gems and the “4th km scale hackathon” event homepage: <https://mpim-po.pages.gwdg.de/km-scale-hackathon/> and links contained therein. The ICON simulations are available in chunked zarr format on HEALPix grid.*

UPDATE December 2024: an updated overview of all the ICON and IFS simulations performed so far, as well as the variables provided, is provided at <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de>.

Is input from other nextGEMS work packages relevant for work in WP3 Production?

Yes

WP2, model development. Production runs in WP3 can only be conducted if work on the SR-ESMs progresses as planned.

M24 (as given by the project plan in the grant agreement).

Does work in WP3 Production depend on external data sources?

No

Actual or expected size of the data produced in WP3 Production?

100TB to 1PB: no concrete estimate available yet.

UPDATE March 2024: *The final output volumes of the nextGEMS production runs produced in WP3 at the time of writing are:*

- *ICON: 460TB*
- *IFS-FESOM: 500 - 600 TB*

The total volume of simulation output produced in nextGEMS so far is in excess on 5PB. This is a result of a number of test simulations which were performed in order to arrive at the final configuration used for the production runs, namely ngc4008 for ICON.

Measures taken in WP3 Production to reduce storage load on shared disk space during the runtime of nextGEMS:

reduction of model output volume, e.g. compression, reduction of output frequency and/or variables (please specify shortly): tbd

automated transfer to tape archive during model runtime, incl. appropriate documentation and/or metadata capture.

deletion of superfluous data.

Will regular backups of data produced in WP3 Production be performed?

yes, of model/tool source code.

nextGEMS -internal use of data produced in WP3 Production:

The initiation and use of the production simulations and their output are identified in the Application Phase of nextGEMS.

Climate change experiments at unprecedented SR resolution will be applied in new avenues of climate change impact research.

Future directions of SR-ESM developments will be identified.

Results from analysis of production simulations inform the modeling path towards DestinE.

UPDATE March 2024: *The WP3 production simulations were used and analysed by more than 100 scientists during the “4th km scale hackathon” in March 2024. More information on the hackathon is available at <https://mpim-po.pages.gwdg.de/km-scale-hackathon/>. Insights gained at the hackathon will be used to further improve the ICON and IFS-FESOM models in terms of their physical realism and biases compared to reanalysis and observational datasets.*

Organization of nextGEMS -internal collaboration based on data produced in WP3 Production:

The exact technical and organisational setting of collaboration on the large-volume output of the production simulations is still to be determined. Similar to the data organisation for the hackathons in development cycles 2 and 3, the bulk of nextGEMS data will be available at DKRZ (either on disk or tape). Data workflows developed until then (in cooperation with other funded projects, e.g. WarmWorld or ACROSS) will most probably facilitate data access and processing.

UPDATE March 2024: *The data availability and data access methods for the nextGEMS production simulations produced in WP3 are documented on and available via [easy.gems](#). Within the nextGEMS project, data handling and access workflows have seen a paradigm shift in the way data is handled. Data is now accessed via intake catalogs, stored in the zarr format and is available on a HEALPix grid - a hierarchical grid allowing efficient access to gridded data at multiple resolutions.*

Will data produced in WP3 Production be published or shared?

Yes, internally for project partners: simulation output from production runs needed for project-internal assessment and tool-development.

Yes, externally for everyone: simulation output as specified in deliverables D3.1 and D3.2.

UPDATE March 2024: *the nextGEMS data published in connection with D3.1 (DOI: https://doi.org/10.26050/WDC/nextGEMS_cyc3)*

UPDATE March 2024: *The publication of the nextGEMS data in connection with D3.2 is underway at the time of writing of this updated DMP. Compared to previous deliverables, the method of publication applied for D3.2 takes a completely new approach of making large-volume SR-ESM datasets available for reuse by the community. In a nutshell, a data catalog (intake and/or STAC) containing references to the production runs will be published via the WDCC, while the data itself remains on the DKRZ infrastructure in such a way that it can be accessed and processed in the same way as done at the “4th km scale hackathon” (see above). DKRZ takes responsibility for the storage of and access to the datasets referenced by the catalog.*

If yes, by which means will data produced in WP3 Production be published or shared?

Data underlying scientific publications will be made available following the FAIR data principles by e.g. making use of DKRZ's WDCC and/or DOKU long-term archiving services, other similar long-term archiving services close to partner institutions and institutional code repositories.

D3.1 Release (publishing in the sense of DOI provision) of Cycle 3 Simulations. (Task 3.1) (M22, AWI) (WDCC publication with DOI).

D3.2 Release (publishing in the sense of DOI provision) of production simulations. (Task 3.2) (M30, MPIM) (WDCC publication with DOI).

UPDATE March 2024: *see directly above*

When will the data produced in WP3 Production be published or shared?

Publication of paper(s) or see timeline given in the nextGEMS grant agreement.

UPDATE March 2024: *The data associated with D3.1 was published in October 2023. D3.2 is planned for mid-April 2024.*

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) produced in WP3 Production be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Own institution

Discipline specific data center: WDCC

4.7.4 Work package WP4/5 Storms & Radiation

Overarching goals of WP4/5 Storms & Radiation

- To stabilize the climate of next-generation models by balancing top-of-atmosphere (TOA) radiation and implement a simplified aerosol scheme, in order to enable studies of Earth's climate sensitivity and aerosol forcing in the Application phase (WP5).

- To identify shortcomings related to remaining sub-grid scale processes, including representation of turbulent transport and mixing, cloud microphysics and subgrid cloud structures.
- To implement online diagnostics of wind energy potential in an innovative bi-directional endeavour, jointly with stakeholders, in order to prepare an assessment of the impacts of changing emissions of CO₂ and aerosols on efforts to replace fossil fuels with renewable energy in the Application phase.
- To test hypotheses, and quantify processes related to aerosols, clouds and their influences on climate change with a new degree of precision and fidelity.
- To develop parametrisations of cloud micro-physics and mixing, and apply advanced data-assimilation methods to model tuning.
- To advance science and support efforts to operationalise the Paris agreement to limit global warming, through improved assessments of aerosol forcing, radiative feedbacks and climate sensitivity.
- To exploit the online diagnostics implemented in the Development phase to investigate the impact of a changing climate on solar and wind energy production in a joint hackathon.

Data categories produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation

climate model output: MISU: ICON atmosphere only, UOXF: ICON-HAM CRM setup.

other model output: UOXF: HAM output, LES.

software/tool: diagnostic code, ICON source code.

Specific datasets produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation

MISU: Wind and solar power diagnostic code, will be developed at and around hackathon 2.

MISU: ICON atmosphere-only simulations to look at feedbacks, forcing and pattern effects.

UOXF: Development of reduced complexity aerosol model HAM, and its implementation in ICON will produce offline and implementation simulation data, from regional to global configuration. Later, production of perturbed aerosol runs with ICON.

KIT: ICON model output, dust emissions, and dust-storm simulation.

LES in support of sub-gridscale parameterizations.

UOXF: ICON-HAM CRM setup, 20-30 runs, 1km resolution, 1000x2000km² domain.

UW: tbd

CNRS: tbd

UH: tbd

UPDATE March 2024: See deliverables available via <https://nextGEMS-h2020.eu/partner-area/>.

Updates will follow in future versions of this DMP.

UPDATE December 2024: *In connection with Deliverable D22 (D4.2), simulations with a reduced complexity aerosol module HAM-Lite were performed. To evaluate the aerosol module, a global simulation with ICON-Sapphire coupled to HAM-lite at a resolution of five kilometers and over a period of 40 days was performed. Aerosols were represented by four modes composed of dust, sea salt, organic carbon, black carbon, and sulfate. The simulation was performed on the Levante cluster of the German Climate Computing Center.*

Parameters/variables which the datasets produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation focus on

Standard ICON model output.

TBD, as it is not clear at this time which parameters are needed and which will be omitted from model output routines.

Is input from other nextGEMS work packages relevant for work in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation?

Yes

ICON and IFS nextGEMS model runs, prepared for hackathons by MPI and ECMWF (WP2).

Current status of model source code, model configurations, model initial and boundary conditions (WP2).

as soon as the WP2 simulations and model source code developments are ready for project use.

Does work in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation depend on external data sources?

Yes

Observational data sets for evaluation, eg EUREC4A.

KIT: These data likely includes observational data, such as satellite or ground-based remote sensing data, existing model simulations from project partners or external sources (e.g. DWD).

KIT: Further, own (re-)used data might include existing source code for model development, or postprocessing and analysis, as well as already processed/manipulated data from external sources.

Actual or expected size of the data produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation?

100TB to 1PB: exact amount tbd

UPDATE December 2024: *The data produced in connection with deliverable D22 (D4.2) amounts to 254TB.*

Measures taken in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation to reduce storage load on shared disk space during the runtime of nextGEMS :

Not specified yet, but needed

UPDATE December 2024: *Concerning the data produced in connection with deliverable D22 (D4.2) (see above), no concrete plans for removing data from shared disk have been put forward yet. However, these data will have to be moved to an externally reachable repository, such as DKRZ's DOKU or WDCC service, in the near future, as a preprint has been submitted to EGU-sphere. Final publication requires the data to be FAIR. Currently, the data are stored on DKRZ's Levante cluster and can be reached at /work/bb1368/b381642/experiments/r2b9_lite_0924g*

Will regular backups of data produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation be performed?

yes, of model/tool source code

nextGEMS -internal use of data produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation:

Analysis of atmosphere-only simulations to look at feedbacks, forcing and pattern effects.

Development of reduced complexity aerosol model based on HAM and its implementation in ICON.

Development of subgrid-scale parameterizations.

Computation of wind and solar diagnostics for use by the renewable energy sector.

UPDATE December 2024: *HAM-lite simulations: NextGEMS groups are already actively working on the data (e.g. Martina Klose on dust).*

Organization of nextGEMS -internal collaboration based on data produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation:

MISU: We would do our best to share data to project partners, but the method will depend on what, how much and on which time scale. When handling large amounts of data there is no single best solution. There is no long term storage options on LUMI, data will need to be moved elsewhere.

UOXF: Simulations are only partly conducted at DKRZ. The process of making data available to project partners (in case this is desired) still has to be sorted out.

KIT: Depending on the HPC system used (e.g. at DKRZ or at KIT), data will be stored at DKRZ or at the Large Scale Data Facility (LSDF) at KIT. In the case that data will be stored at KIT, download of data or remote access to the data sets via THREDDS data server (TDS) or S3 object storage can be provided. Depending on which system is used, there are different protocols to work with the data sets via remote access frameworks (OpeNDAP, CSW, URL etc.). While this tools cover data sharing during ongoing working processes repositories like Radar4KIT (<https://radar.kit.edu>), Pangaea (<https://www.pangaea.de>) or WDCC (<https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cersearch/>) can be used to share and cite final data sets. Regardless of which system is used, sharing communities should be defined if the data won't be open source. Those sharing communities will build the basis to define access rights.

UPDATE December 2024: *HAM-lite simulations: the data is available on DKRZ's Levante cluster at /work/bb1368/b381642/experiments/r2b9_lite_0924g and is already used by other groups*

of the consortium.

Will data produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation be published or shared?

Yes, internally for project partners: model source code developments, intermediate evaluation results, diagnostic code.

Yes, externally for everyone: project data underlying scientific publications.

If yes, by which means will data produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation be published or shared?

WDCC/DOKU @DKRZ

(<https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cersearch/info?site=submitinfo>)

Radar4KIT (<https://radar.kit.edu>)

Pangaea (<https://www.pangaea.de>)

Data underlying scientific publications will be made available following the FAIR data principles by e.g. making use of DKRZ's WDCC and/or DOKU long-term archiving services, other similar long-term archiving services close to partner institutions and institutional code repositories.

When will the data produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation be published or shared?

Publication of paper(s) or see timeline given in the nextGEMS grant agreement.

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) produced in WP4/5 Storms & Radiation be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Discipline specific data center: WDCC, PANGAEA

Generic data center: RADAR4KIT

4.7.5 Work package WP6/7 Storms & Ocean

Overarching goals of WP6/7 Storms & Ocean

- To identify and evaluate key ocean and marine atmosphere features in the SR-ESM simulations of all three development cycles.
- To validate the marine planetary boundary layer representation of the SR-ESM simulations.
- To provide ocean initial conditions for the coupled SR-ESM simulations.
- To provide developments towards an ocean mixed layer scheme adequate for SR-ESMs.
- To create numerical tools that generate output streams useful to the planetary boundary layer, ocean mixedlayer and fisheries communities.
- To identify the importance of meso-scale air-sea interaction on tropical climate, on its

dominant patterns of variability and teleconnections, and on its response to global warming

- To appraise the significance of resolving atmospheric convection and storm-scales for simulating the West African Monsoon (WAM) and hydrological cycle extremes, and their response to global warming.

- To evaluate the influence of mesoscales on tropical cyclones and on their response to global warming.
- To assess the impacts of climate and climate change on global primary productivity, and global and West African fisheries using SR-ESMs.
- To anticipate the relevance of resolving mesoscale circulations for global climate change assessments.
- To evaluate and refine new ocean mixed layer and planetary boundary layer representation in the coupled system.

Data categories produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean

other model output: ICON-O, FESOM2

model-data evaluation products: UCM: model evaluation based on observational datasets

other: observations database

Specific datasets produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean

GEOMAR, NBI: In situ observation of large mixing events in the tropical mixed layer.

MPI-M: ICON-O stand-alone simulations at r2b8 (10km) and ocean spin-up simulations at r2b9 (5km) resolution.

MPI-M: ICON-O sensitivity experiments (r2b8), 3-5 experiments of 5-10 years length.

AWI: stand-alone FESOM2 simulations forced by ERA5; 3-5 experiments of 5-10 years length.

AWI: stand-alone, ERA5 forced spin-up simulation at NG5 resolution, 10 years long.

AWI: stand-alone, ERA5 forced spin-up at Rossby 4.1 resolution for the final IFS/FESOM simulations.

UCM: model evaluation analysis.

UUREAD, IRD, ISRA: to be determined.

UPDATE March 2024: See deliverables available via <https://nextGEMS-h2020.eu/partner-area/>. Updates will follow in future versions of this DMP.

Parameters/variables which the datasets produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean focus on

GEOMAR, NBI: parameters relevant to ocean mixing.

MPI-M: ICON-O output and output necessary for ESM coupling (spin-up simulations).

AWI: FESOM output and output necessary for ESM coupling (spin-up simulations).

Is input from other nextGEMS work packages relevant for work in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean?

Yes

GEOMAR, NBI: no.

AWI, MPI-M: maybe, depends on suitability of simulations produced for the individual nextGEMS cycles.

UCM: Data from simulations (WP2) whenever available.

Whenever available, at least in the framework of nextGEMS Hackathons.

Does work in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean depend on external data sources?

Yes

GEOMAR, NBI: observational data products.

MPI-M, AWI: ERA5 reanalysis data (available at DKRZ).

UCM: Observation and reanalysis data to compare with simulations (ERA5, GPCP, CRU, CMAP, CPC, HadISST, ERSST, OISST, ORAS5, SODA342).

Actual or expected size of the data produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean?

100TB to 1PB: ca 150 TB (MPI-M and AWI ocean runs).

Measures taken in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean to reduce storage load on shared disk space during the runtime of nextGEMS:

automated transfer to tape archive during model runtime, incl. appropriate documentation and/or metadata capture.

transfer of not frequently used datasets to tape archive.

Will regular backups of data produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean be performed?

yes, of all relevant data.

yes, of model/tool source code.

nextGEMS-internal use of data produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean:

GEOMAR: Model evaluation (ocean).

MPI-M and AWI: stand-alone model simulations are used to test parameterisations.

MPI-M and AWI: spin-up simulations will be used by WP2 and WP3 to perform the coupled SR-ESM simulations.

Organization of nextGEMS -internal collaboration based on data produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean:

GEOMAR, NBI: data will be shared with project partners during the course of the project. Technical realisation to be determined.

MPI-M and AWI: stand-alone ocean simulations are performed at DKRZ and will be made available to all project partners. **UCM:** results from model evaluation will be fed back to the model development WPs **UREAD, IRD:** to be determined

Will data produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean be published or shared?

Yes, internally for project partners: ocean spin-up as basis for Cycle2, 3 and production simulations; ocean model evaluation results.

Yes, externally for everyone: project data underlying scientific publications.

UPDATE March 2024: *Output of the WP6 ocean vertical mixing sensitivity runs associate with deliverable D32 (D6.4) is published in the WDCC and is available via DOI: https://doi.org/10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_WP6oc*

UPDATE December 2024: *The database of synoptic oceaning mixing events which can be used for model evaluation produced in the framework of Deliverable D31 (D6.3) is published at PANGAEA and is available via its DOI: <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.964320>.*

If yes, by which means will data produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean be published or shared?

Data underlying scientific publications will be made available following the FAIR data principles by e.g. making use of DKRZ's WDCC and/or DOKU long-term archiving services and institutional code repositories.

More specific: Selected datasets (e.g. sensitivity experiments used for publications) will be available to the general community using suitable infrastructure available.

When will the data produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean be published or shared?

UPDATE December 2024: *Data associated with deliverables D31 and D32 has been made available via public repositories at the time of deliverable submission (see above).*

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) produced in WP6/7 Storms & Ocean be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Discipline specific data center: PANGAEA, WDCC.

4.7.6 Work package WP8/9 Storms & Land

Overarching goals of WP8/9 Storms & Land

- Evaluate surface energy, water and momentum balance components as well as near-surface meteorology over land at storm-resolving resolution against observations and coarser resolution simulations.

- Represent land-surface heterogeneities at storm-resolving resolution by making use of the latest generation remote sensing products of land cover and vegetation.
- Prepare the nextGEMS models to best serve the science and applications, by implementing online output statistics co-developed with stakeholders, with a pilot project focusing on solar energy.
- Expand scope of the SR-ESM by coupling it offline to a terrestrial biosphere model.
- Investigate whether resolving the storm-scale variability in weather systems and in the land surface, together with their consistent interactions with the larger scales, affects the climatology of blocking, the statistics of dry and warm spells, the mean surface radiation balance as well as near-term changes in aggregated temperature and precipitation statistics.
- Quantify the carbon stocks and fluxes over Europe at storm-resolving resolution and compare these estimates to ones from current ESMs.
- Use the production runs to reassess solar power on the global scale and to produce global maps of hazardous weather at unprecedented resolution.

Data categories produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land

model-data evaluation products: IPMA: land surface temperature from satellite observations; WU: model evaluation with supersite data at specific locations.

Specific datasets produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land

IPMA: monthly and seasonal mean diurnal cycles of land surface temperature derived from geostationary satellite observations.

WU: outcomes of model evaluation against supersite data.

MPIM, UBERN, ETHZ: to be determined.

UPDATE March 2024: See deliverables available via <https://nextGEMS-h2020.eu/partner-area/>. Updates will follow in future versions of this DMP.

Parameters/variables which the datasets produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land focus on

IPMA: land surface temperature (derived from satellite observations).

Is input from other nextGEMS work packages relevant for work in WP8/9 Storms & Land?

Yes

IPMA, WU: IFS and ICON simulations produced in WP2.

IPMA, WU: throughout the project.

Does work in WP8/9 Storms & Land depend on external data sources?

Yes

IPMA: MSG geostationary land surface temperatures produced in the framework of LandSAF. Further information: <https://landsaf.ipma.pt/en/products/land-surface-temperature/lst/>.

WU: data from observational sites, including the CESAR observatory in Cabauw, The Netherlands, the Lindenberg Observatory for the evaluation of the models in WP8 and the further analysis of the data in WP9. This is throughout the final three years of the project. The Cabauw data is available at <https://ruisdael-observatory.nl/cesar/>. Lindenberg data is available throughout de DWD website.

Actual or expected size of the data produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land?

1TB to 100TB: IPMA: 2.2TB (original LandSAF data).

UPDATE December 2024: *The data produced in connection with deliverable D41 (D8.2) amounts to approximately 30GB. These data were used to reformulate the land surface description in the IFS model.*

The data produced in connection with D45 (D8.6) amounted to approximately 1TB.

Measures taken in WP8/9 Storms & Land to reduce storage load on shared disk space during the runtime of nextGEMS:

not applicable to this WP.

Will regular backups of data produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land be performed?

yes, of model/tool source code.

nextGEMS -internal use of data produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land:

IPMA: monthly and seasonal mean diurnal cycles of land surface temperature produced in this WP will be used to evaluate model simulations.

WU: analysis of data from ICON and IFS and comparison against station data at location to be determined (see supersite data which is planned to be used).

MPIM: to be determined

Organization of nextGEMS -internal collaboration based on data produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land:

IPMA: since the original data is freely available, the processed data can be also made available to the project partners and/or general community. But for that we would need to have a data repository.

WU: Processed data will be freely available to other researchers.

Will data produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land be published or shared?

Yes, internally for project partners: compiled datasets used for model evaluation; model evaluation results.

Yes, externally for everyone: project data underlying scientific publications.

UPDATE December 2024: *The data produced in connection with D41 (D8.2) is currently stored on DKRZ's Levante cluster and is available at /work/bm1235/b381679/urban_stuff/LST/LSA_SAF. However, there is no apparent requirements by other consortium partners for this data apart from the IFS modeling team. Therefore, the new land cover maps for the IFS model are also archived at ECMWF.*

The data produced in connection with D45 (D8.6) has been deleted after the completion of the deliverable and is thus not available. The setup and approach will be used in task 9.4 to estimate carbon stocks and fluxes over Europe and these estimations will be open access and documented in the upcoming deliverable D9.4.

If yes, by which means will data produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land be published or shared?

Data underlying scientific publications will be made available following the FAIR data principles by e.g. making use of DKRZ's WDCC and/or DOKU long-term archiving services and institutional code repositories.

WU: Data from observational sites will follow the data policy of the respective stations. Processed data by our work package will be freely available to other researchers.

IPMA: since the original data is freely available, the processed data can be also made available to the project partners and/or general community. But for that we would need to have a data repository.

UPDATE December 2024: *Scientific publications are planned in the context of the land-surface reformulation work done for IFS. Data will be made available alongside the publications using established repositories, e.g. WDCC, PANGAEA or zenodo.*

When will the data produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land be published or shared?

Publication of paper(s) or see timeline given in the nextGEMS grant agreement.

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) produced in WP8/9 Storms & Land be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Own institution.

Discipline specific data center: WDCC, PANGAEA.

4.7.7 Work package WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication

Overarching goals of WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication

- Implement, monitor and adjust an effective strategy for nextGEMS coproduction, communication & dissemination and video presence.
- Connect model development and application communities and integrate potential users

into the coproduction activities (coproduction process).

- Develop novel communication and dissemination forms to maximize the visibility and usability of the project and its results to target audiences (communication and dissemination).
- Provide technical and policy briefings to the competent authorities to make them aware of project results (policy dissemination).

Data categories produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication

other: Storylines, research videos (vlog), survey data.

Specific datasets produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication

Outreach and Communication Videos.

Survey among hackathon participants as basis for social network analysis.

Storylines.

Parameters/variables which the datasets produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication focus on

not applicable to this WP.

Is input from other nextGEMS work packages relevant for work in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication?

Yes.

Input from all project participants is needed to create the envisaged data products.

Throughout the project.

Does work in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication depend on external data sources?

No

Actual or expected size of the data produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication?

less than 1TB

Measures taken in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication to reduce storage load on shared disk space during the runtime of nextGEMS:

not applicable to this WP.

transfer of not frequently used datasets to tape archive.

Will regular backups of data produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication be performed?

yes, of all relevant data.

nextGEMS -internal use of data produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication:

BSC: The collected data will be analysed using social network analysis.

WP10 will, in collaboration with other project themes and users, develop storylines. At least two storylines will be developed. The storyline on renewable energy will depend on data produced in WP5, as well as the knowledge coproduced in collaboration with project partners and users from the renewable energy sector. The deadline for the final storyline is M46, but we expect an earlier version by M36 so that the results can be shared and finetuned with other users. The storyline on fisheries and food security in Western Africa will depend on data produced in WP7 and the knowledge coproduced with the project partner and users from fisheries, as well as policy makers. The final deadline for this storyline is M46, but an early draft should be available by M36, so that results can be presented in workshops and other events to the broader user and policy community.

LT: produced videos will display and communicate the project goals and progress as well as scientist portraits in the framework of a Vlog.

Organization of nextGEMS -internal collaboration based on data produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication:

BSC: Survey data about the relationships between hackathon participants will be collected at each hackathon. Results of the social network analysis will be made available via reports or papers.

LT: videos are created in conjunction with the nextGEMS scientists and are embedded into the projects' homepage.

Will data produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication be published or shared?

Yes, internally for project partners: intermediate results of social network analysis.

Yes, externally for everyone: report/publication using anonymised data from the social network analysis, videos, science explainers, communication material.

No: raw data from social network analysis

UPDATE March 2024: A collection of information material consisting of fact sheets and scientific explainer videos is available via the nextGEMS project homepage at <https://nextGEMS-h2020.eu>.

If yes, by which means will data produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication be published or shared?

BSC: The results of the social network analysis will be publicly available, either through reports or through research papers. All data will be anonymized and presented in an aggregated form.

LT: videos will be published via the nextGEMS homepage: <https://nextGEMS-h2020.eu/> and are hosted via LT's Vimeo account: <https://vimeo.com/latestthinking>.

When will the data produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication be published or shared?

UPDATE March 2024: *Data products, especially those produced by LT, are published via the above-mentioned channels as they are produced. For example, material produced in connection with the nextGEMS hackathons is available several weeks after the event takes place.*

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) produced in WP10 Storms & Society, Knowledge Coproduction, Dissemination & Communication be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Has not yet been decided

4.7.8 Work package WP11 Ethics requirements

Overarching goals of WP11 Ethics requirements

This work package sets out the 'ethics requirements' that the project must comply with.

Data categories produced in WP11 Ethics requirements

other: Protection of personal data (POPD) guidelines

Specific datasets produced in WP11 Ethics requirements

POPD - requirement No. 3

Parameters/variables which the datasets produced in WP11 Ethics requirements focus on

not applicable to this WP.

Is input from other nextGEMS work packages relevant for work in WP11 Ethics requirements?

No

n/a

Does work in WP11 Ethics requirements depend on external data sources?

No

Actual or expected size of the data produced in WP11 Ethics requirements?

less than 1TB

Measures taken in WP11 Ethics requirements to reduce storage load on shared disk space during the runtime of nextGEMS :

not applicable to this WP.

Will regular backups of data produced in WP11 Ethics requirements be performed?

yes, of all relevant data.

nextGEMS -internal use of data produced in WP11 Ethics requirements:

This work package sets out the 'ethics requirements' that the project must comply with.

Organization of nextGEMS -internal collaboration based on data produced in WP11 Ethics requirements:

Available to project members via the projects' cloud storage (contact the project office for more information).

Will data produced in WP11 Ethics requirements be published or shared?

Yes, internally for project partners: POPD document (deliverable D11.1).

If yes, by which means will data produced in WP11 Ethics requirements be published or shared?

GWDG cloud service

When will the data produced in WP11 Ethics requirements be published or shared?

According to deliverable publication defined in grant agreement (M3 of the project).

Where will the data (including metadata, documentation and, if applicable, relevant code) produced in WP11 Ethics requirements be stored or archived after the end of the project?

Has not yet been decided.

5 Dissemination and uptake

5.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

5.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

UPDATE March 24: *This updated DMP will be made publicly available via the NextGEMS homepage (<https://nextgems-h2020.eu/partner-area/>). Further, communication of this deliverable as foreseen and executed by the EU Commission will take place.*

6 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

yes

The deliverable was delayed due to the workload and duties of the people involved during the preparations for the fourth nextGEMS hackathon in early March 2024. The delay was communicated with and approved by our project officer.

7 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

8 Sustainability

Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

UPDATE March 2024: *The completion of the updated DMP critically depends on the contributions of all project work packages. Concerning deliverables, the NextGEMS DMP is closely connected to completed deliverables D2.2 and D3.1, as these are concerned with making project data available in-line with the FAIR principles. Concerning connections to other projects, the work on data management in NextGEMS clearly benefits from connections to the BMBF-funded WarmWorld project and the EURO-HPC Centre of Excellence ESiWACE3.*

9 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19. – 22. October 2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 01. – 03. April 2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26. June – 02. July 2022 in Vienna
- Storms & Ocean summer slackathon 31. June – 06. July 2022 at the Bornö Institute for ocean and climate studies, Sweden
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023
- Mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04. – 06. April 2023
- Cycle 3 Hackathon 29. May – 02. June 2023 in Madrid
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2024
- 4th km-scale hackathon, 4 – 8 March 2024 in Hamburg

10 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextGEMS-h2020.eu/publications/>